

NEURO - EXPERIMENT IN **ENTREPRENEURIAL CHOICE MAKING**

(SYNOPSIS)

Prologue

The era of neuromanagement has arrived carrying along with it the world of neuro - entrepreneurship. Researchers in Psychology, primarily neuro - psychology, engaged in neuro - entrepreneurship choice issues need to get linked with this new scholarship as to notice multi - disciplinary and inter - disciplinary off - shoots. Research efforts carried out, that form the bedrock of this thesis, by Colonel Dr J Satpathy (hereafter, Candidate) was in area of neuromanagement with thrust on neuro - choice behaviourism in entrepreneurship and business.

In 2021, Candidate published papers (and, posters) under the titles, 'Behavioural Transmitters', 'Cerebral Guesstimates', 'Disruptive Blood Guesstimates', 'Face Recognition', 'Hematological Signatures', 'Hemato - Psychological Designs, 'Disruptive Neuro - Heretical in Heterodox Choice', 'Avant-Garde Stratagems', 'Neuro - Hematological Strategy', 'HR Curvatures', 'Hemato- Cerebral Choice', 'Hemachocivation', and 'Hematological Signatures', to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2020, published papers (and, posters) in, Neuro - Calibrations, 'Behaviour Department', 'Neuro - Milieus', 'Entrepreneurship and Technology: Future Trends', Neuro - Reflections in Work - Family Enrichment', 'Traversing Work - Life Equilibrium with Mindfulness', 'Tabula Rasa' Personnel Entrepreneur', 'Perceptive Entrepreneurial Choice Comportment', Noetic Alleyways: Choosing to Choose or Deciding to Decide, 'Behavioural Neuromangement', 'Neuro - Couplings', 'Neuro -Cursors', 'Choice Mosaic', 'Neuroentrepreneurial Preference', 'Skin Conductance', 'Neuro - Smidgeons' (Poster), 'Ophthalmological Catalysts' (Poster), 'Neuro - Curvatures' (Poster), 'Neuro - Heterodoxies', 'Choice Topography', 'Neuro - Trajectories', 'Computational Neuro - Trajectories' 'Neuro - Genetic Underpinnings' and 'Cognitive Reconnaissance', to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2019, published papers (and, posters) included, ‘Skin Conductance in ‘Smart’ Entrepreneurial Judgement’, ‘Visual Monikers’, ‘Competency Plotting’, ‘Neuro - Evidence’, ‘Digitalised Neuro - Choice Making’, ‘Personality, Neuro - Trust and LMX’, ‘Ophthalmic Signatures’, ‘Neuro - Diagonals’, ‘Neuro - Geometry’, ‘Oculo - Empirical Signatures’, ‘Neuro - Economic ‘Agent’, ‘Neuro - Monikers’, ‘Oculo - Tactical Monikers’, ‘Neuro - Preference Connectionism’, ‘Neuro - Capability’, ‘Neurophysiological Drivers (Poster)’, ‘Choice Uncertainties’, ‘Neuro - Optometric Estimates’, ‘Electrodermal Traces’ and ‘Cardio - Peep’ (Poster), to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2018, published papers (and, posters) included, ‘Socio - Genetic Matrices’ (Case Study), ‘Human Capital: Neuro - Based Analysis’, ‘Neuro - Choice Undercurrents’, ‘Neuroreductionist Approaches’, ‘Entrepreneurial Skills’, ‘Choice Signatures’ (Poster), ‘Choice Monikers’, ‘Cognitive ‘Agent’, ‘Hematological Insight’, ‘Hematological Judgement’, and ‘Mathematical Exposition in Choice Dynamics, to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2017, published papers (and, posters) included, ‘Neuro - Organisational Choice Comportment’, ‘Romancing Neurodecision Making’, ‘Review on Neuroentrepreneurial Choice Crescendo’s’, ‘No Food, No Water: What Choice Making’, ‘Neuro - Hybrid Architecture’ and ‘Brain - Eye Coadjuvancy’, to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

In 2016, published papers (and, posters) included, ‘Cognitive Underpinning’ (Poster), ‘Unmapped Territory’, ‘Crafting Neuro Economic - Choices’, ‘Neuro - Operables’, ‘Neuro - Contemplation’ and Neuro - Geometry. A list of papers (and, posters) is appended to this thesis. Candidate published SSRN - ELSEVIER papers, between 2016 and 2021 under the titles, ‘Voyage into Neuro’, ‘Proclaiming Neurosocioconomics’, ‘Introducing Neuroentrepreneurial Models’, ‘Postulates in Neuro - Choice Making’ and ‘Behavioural Transmitters, to list a few. A list of papers (and, posters) by the Candidate is appended to this thesis.

Introduction

Life is full of choices and selections as human beings are ‘Thinking Agents’. Human behaviour is not the product of a single process, but rather reflects interaction of different

specialized subsystems. As old as Civilization and fruition of Earth, choice making is rudimentary humanoid action. 21st Century is baptized to be ‘Century of Human Brain, Blood and Eyes’; a complex playfield in business choice perspectives. With birth of a new scientific field, experts have taxed to comprehend how we make choices by using different approaches. Important question is how individuals make choices. Researchers are interested in assumptions, beliefs, habits and tactics used to make choices. Research suggests that brain considers various sources of information before making a choice. However, how does it do this? In addition, why does the process sometimes go awry, causing impulsive, indecisive and confused choices; that lead to risky and potentially dangerous behaviours? Result is that brain sometimes argues with itself, as these distinct systems come to different conclusions about what we should do. Human behaviour is not under constant and detailed control of careful and accurate hedonic calculations. It is product of an unstable and irrational complex of reflex actions, impulses, instincts and habits.

This is a world of choices, alternatives, options, utility and optimization; VUCA (Vulnerability, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity). Appreciable reflections have been directed toward choice making process that confront an entrepreneur (case in query in this thesis). How do entrepreneurs make an optimal choice? How do entrepreneurs bargain ‘hot buttons’ and influence entrepreneurial brain, blood and eye(s) in business choices? Questions that need to be answered include; how to choose in tough situations where stakes are high and there are multiple conflicting objectives? How should entrepreneurs’ plan? How can we deal with risks and uncertainties involved in a choice? How can we create options that are better than the ones originally available? How can we become better choice makers? What resources will be invested in choice - making? What are the potential responses to a particular problem or opportunity? Who will make this choice? Every prospective action has strengths and weaknesses; how should they be evaluated? These are the questions neuroentrepreneurial researchers suspect are most crucial for understanding complex human behaviours. This affords conceptual geometry for conducting neuro (entrepreneurial) choice research through measurement of neural activity at management levels of analysis. Research investigates neural bases of choice predictability and value as central parameters in expected utility to choice making. Integration of these offers exciting potential for construction of near - accurate models of choice - making. In such a mosaic of conditions, it becomes vivacious to fruitage powerful, astute businesses that generate enthusiastic doppelgänger of entrepreneurship.

Neuromanagement exhibits that brain behaves differently when facing nature or human actors. Few management investigators are passionate to study character of neuromanagement in entrepreneurial choice making dynamics. Neuromanagement translational research arrange for new way of computing entrepreneurial choice. 'Inferential' information and neuroscientific representations stimulate to start a fresh inquiry with tests choice observables and computational (neural) mechanisms. Motivation prompted to explore links between entrepreneurial choice making and neuroscience. It was significant to arrive at a conclusion that neuroscience and neuromanagement follow 'Biological Plausibility' (causal connection between presumed origin and outcome that is unswerving with prevailing biotic understanding).

Research Statement

All entrepreneurs face complex circumstances of hard events to take paramount choice, weighing optimistic / unenthusiastic aspects and obliged to accept risk. Some selected inquiries adopted for inquiries are; How to account information about value, risk, ambiguity and timing? How does this criterion behave with orientation to the chosen approach? What distinguishes criteria adopted is dissimilar? Are there direct correlations that exist between approaches? How identifiable variables affect selection of choice making criteria? Is there a relationship between external variables and choice criterion used? What kinds of algorithms and computations underpin choice process?

Emerging neuroentrepreneurial science evidence suggests that sound and rational neuroentrepreneurial choice making depends on prior accurate emotional processing. Somatic marker hypothesis provides a systems-level neuroentrepreneurial anatomical and cognitive framework for neuroentrepreneurial choice making and its influence. These occur at multiple levels of operation. Some occur consciously and some non-consciously. Issues that crop up are; what happens when entrepreneurs change minds? What algorithms allow sensorimotor behaviours to be learned? What computational mechanisms allow brain to adapt changing circumstances? How (and where) are value and probability combined in brain and what is the dynamics of this? What neural systems track defined forms of utility? To what extent do utility computations generalize to choice, which are tasks that are more complex? How do systems that focus on immediate choices interact?

Research statement adopted for this inquiry is despite advances, question of how entrepreneur make business choices continues to pose challenges. Research statement

encases; what is the character of entrepreneurial choice dynamics and how do they come around? How do entrepreneurial practices change over time? What agents influence (re) configuration of entrepreneurial practices? How do entrepreneurial practices transmit to entrepreneurial behaviour and abilities? How and why do practices relay implementation probability? How and why do entrepreneurs endorse choice making approaches?

Objective(s) and Scope

Principal gap observed is that there is no rock solid evidence as regards any study centring on role of blood monikers and eye movements in entrepreneurial choice making, barring a negligible few. This research is perhaps step forward research by using tools from neuro - management. This attempt does generate indications for manifold arrangements involved in entrepreneurs' choice making. Principal attempt was to cast eye on tumultuous issues engulfing world of business and primarily that of choice processing. Care has been allotted for 'disruptive mental' approximations'. This is from a principle - based outlook to report research problem based on empirical study. Principal aim is to model entrepreneurs' choice making by using tools from neuro - management. This translational thesis presents neuro-entrepreneurial science of management modelling approach. This was to create evidences for multiple systems involved in entrepreneurs' choice-making. Besides principal objective, following objectives have been taken into consideration for present translational research work; criteria (physiognomies that each alternative own) adopted for choice making, methodology of assessing cases for choice making, variables that emphasizes choice making, choice perspectives as regards (UVCA)andconduct neuro - based interpretation on entrepreneurs' choice making.

Objective of this inquiry is to identify neural processes involved in entrepreneurial choice making. It aims to transport diversity of disciplinary backgrounds to probe into how business choices are made. Attempt contributes to offer inter - disciplinary perceptions of brain and eye(s) activity at time of entrepreneurial choice making to include exploring anatomy of neuro - discourses to functions of 'neuro - biologism'.

Backbone of this thesis embodies translational research depicting link between management and entrepreneurial neuromanagement to explicate how choice makers inter-disciplinary field translational research makes choice by integrating psychology, neuroscience and management science. Attempt encompasses irregularities that are gainsay

with traditional entrepreneurial hypotheses, appraise choice making by combining methods such as behavioural, neurophysiological, experimental economics and develop choice models based on neural and psychological mechanism. Through computational approaches, attempt have been to clarify how neural circuits realize ‘mental simulation’ in entrepreneurial choice-making. This plan ventures to offer a model about relationship between eye movements and blood monikers and underlying neuroentrepreneurial underpinnings involved in choice - making.

By characterizing effect of these influences, this study expects to gain insight into how eye movements and blood monikers compute choice-making. this work would attempt to explore phenomena through individual action, choice-making, and reasoning processes on concept of cognitive models of choice - making. Principal aim of proposed study has been to model neuroentrepreneurial basis of choice making by using tools from blood monikers and eye movements. Purpose has been to elucidate principles and choice - making mechanism in brain interaction between variables of blood monikers and eye movements processes. Focal point is to understand neural processes underlying how entrepreneurs craft choices and choices, understand mechanisms of choice - making and integrating interdisciplinary research towards contributing to neuroentrepreneurial choice.

Originality and Relevance

Goal of studying human choice behaviour is prediction. This research seeks to develop theoretical models, based on axiomatic foundation of eye movements and blood monikers, which can predict entrepreneurial choices. These models would take as inputs state of external world and generate as outputs actual choices made by human choosers. For this reason, research aims towards achieving compact and abstract models of choice. To date, management model of choice has not been informed by the way blood monikers and eye movements functions. Analysis of observations include not only choices between options, per se, but additional eye movements and blood monikers data, including length of time taken to make choices, number of error in choices and psychophysical model(s).

Including more than just observed choices allows data to have an additional disciplining effect on theory. This thesis extends this assumption of optimal behaviour to analysis of blood monikers and eye movements process producing a choice. To do this, thesis assumes that there is an unobservable choice that an agent makes, consequences of which are reflected in all observable data that can be measured in the choice process. That choice is

strength of effort devoted to processing blood monikers and eye movements information in reaching a choice between options. As a conclusion, attempt has been to propose a model that links predictions of traditional psychological observations and predictions of relative blood monikers and eye movements activation dependent on exogenous characteristics of choice environment. Neuroentrepreneurial management model will play a crucial role in building of new reliable theories capable of explaining and predicting individual behaviour and strategic choices. Main message is that individual is not one coherent body. Blood monikers and eye movements are a multi-system entity and therefore choice-maker must be modelled as an organisation. Systematic study of interactions between agents and choice processes lead to novel insights. Applying similar methodology to study entrepreneurial choice - making is the way to understand bounds of rationality.

Until now, research has not systematically integrated influence of sub - systems of blood monikers and eye movements in choice-making. Evidence suggests that choice - making depends on methodical methods to analyse relevant blood monikers and eye movements processes. Due to its multidisciplinary nature, this investigation is subject to several kinds of misconceptions. While there are several benefits of using neuroentrepreneurial techniques in understanding choice making, there are questions that neuroentrepreneurial science cannot answer by itself and needs help of experimental methodology and theories to understand how Entrepreneurs decide. The key limitation is identifying different regions of blood monikers and eye movements in certain situations (VUCA). These techniques are not able to provide an explanation or a reason (neuroentrepreneurial) as to why we respond in the manner that we do. What happens in blood monikers and eye movements or what is activated when entrepreneurs make choices or are in process of making choices or responding to outcomes? It does not give insight into why we make choices and why we respond in the manner that we do. This is where experimental methodology would help bolster understanding. A synergy between neuroentrepreneurial techniques and experiments provide insight into understanding Entrepreneurial choice making.

Thesis revolves around 'human beings' and entrepreneurs as principal agents who attempt to 'push' towards constancy in choice dynamics. Thesis presents 'biology - inspired entrepreneurial science' revolutions that originate from management (science of 'choice behaviour') and psychology (discipline of 'thought') with reference to blood monikers and

eye movements, blood and eye(s). Attempt has been made to reveal as to how rational events are concomitant to neurophysiological chronicles. There are efforts to reveal blood monikers and eye movements, blood and eye(s) interrelations to appreciate how and why entrepreneurs make choices. Orientations have been made to compendium of subjects that challenge research. Entrepreneurial issues have been underlined that rear few central issues and offer solution through 'rationalism' scrutiny. Inspiration for undertaking this investigation has been accessible with potential to propose central change in how entrepreneurs think, perceive and model choice. Role of neuromanagement, blood monikers and eye movements and eye (s), opinions and sentiments, neurons, psychology, behavioural controlling, cognitive and sentimental neuroscience, entrepreneurial sciences, that possibly deliver answer to issues in entrepreneurial choice dynamics has been anticipated with orientation to 'Biological ('mental effort') Plausibility'. Entrepreneurial neuro - linkages have been initiated that develop around hematological, blood monikers and eye movements imaging and ocular (eye movements) considerations. Some empirical processes have been recommended that address core problem in conceptual choice exploration and advance fresh questions? Challenging observations, including some unexplained difficulties and objectives of proposed inquiry have been acknowledged.

Thesis rationales to present inter - disciplinary review of some neuro - based theories and methods used in entrepreneurial choice making. Challenge is to promote knowledge that apply outside lab and address complex challenges. Thesis relates assimilated entrepreneurial -psychological viewpoint. To conduct a comprehensive review of literature pertaining to a dynamic and interdisciplinary subject of scholarship viz. neuro-preference architecture, review defied its scope with published journal thesis and books plus research literatures linked to bases, philosophies, methods and principles of neuro-preference architecture. Some key words punched for purpose of reviews was neuro - preference, neuro - architecture, types, methods, classification of neuro-preference-architecture, neuro - preference reinforcement, neuro - facilitation, neuro-preference reduction, neuro - preference deficiencies, neuro-preference optimization, neuro-preference assessment and neuro-preference evaluation. Secondary sources were primarily from published literatures and web search engines, along with personal communication via. Mail with resource persons. Thesis describes rudimentary strengths and weaknesses of each neuro - behavioural characteristic with key references. Reviews include theories, investigational facts, figures, statistics, deductions, axioms, corollaries, inferences, conjectures and results

of earlier studies well established in chosen area of inquiry; blood monikers, blood monikers and eye movements and eye(s). Focal point revolves around; neural routes underlying how entrepreneurs design preferences, understand methodologies of preference architecture by using imaging methodologies and integrating transdisciplinary research to preference management.

Research Methodology

Aim of this thesis is to comprehend subjects' relevance judgment based on blood monikers eye tracking method. Fundamental inquiry has two components; First, how subjects' blood monikers and eye tracking 'inferential' data are concomitant with fortitude of bearing of portions of content displayed. Next, connections crop up between blood monikers and eye tracking 'inferential' data with cognitive loads ('mental effort') during exploration tasks? Besides analysing questionnaire responses, principal methodologies adopted for this inquiry are Hematological tests and Eye Movement tests.

Thesis presents gist of experiments, results obtained, inferences drawn and general discussion on 'Cause' and 'Effect' relationship in gamut of entrepreneurial choice making. Thesis emphasizes principally on abstract concerns involved in selecting inquiry method and estimating results by means of diverse practices. Principal aim was to conduct experiments by likening its message / outcome implications with experimental observations, explore causes, establish empirical regularities as basis for new theory, comparing environments by protuberance of neural activity. Research methodology is based upon deductive inter - disciplinary review approach.

Thesis attempts to employ multi - method approach and triangulation. In light of discussing theories and applications of neuroentrepreneurial science in choice making, sophisticated techniques have emerged to understand neural activity and how brains respond to stimuli in brain. Blood monikers and eye movements could precisely localize areas activated when subjects perform various human processes with concentration on formulating research question, designing protocol, analyzing data and interpreting / reporting results. The proposed methodology helped develop theoretical foundations, models and algorithms to support near-optimal choice making in highly complex, dynamic systems, operating in uncertain, resource-constrained situation.

As regards population and sample size, it is estimated that a population of 150 respondents was deemed a fair population and subjecting respondents to clinical test led to fair results. As regards research design, research was based on questionnaires and interviews with a view to soliciting primary data. Secondary data was extracted from available secondary sources. The usual statistical tools like SPSS, ANOVA, MANOVA and Data Analysis software was considered as deemed fit. As regards clinical primary data, study undertook lab - based neuro - experiments via. Blood monikers and eye movements. For purpose of blood monikers identification, complete blood count analyser equipment was applied. For purpose of eye movements, Tobii eye tracker was applied. Results obtained from statistical tools were compared and contrasted with clinical tools for real - time picture of how an entrepreneur arrives at a choice threshold.

Research Methodology and Results

To provide central basis for understanding entrepreneurial choice making and rational centric choice poise, research analyzed blood samples of willing and volunteer respondents. It is perceived that almost all 'Hematological Monikers' in respondents reflect disquieting trends. Based on clinical tests, it is inferred that; rational centric choice making potential is bad when;

- Blood glucose fasting indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Blood glucose post - prandial indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Blood glucose random indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Urea indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Creatine indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Sodium indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Potassium indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- S bilirubin direct indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- S bilirubin indirect indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Aspartate trans amines AST indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Alanine trans amines alt indices are seeming as 'atypical'.
- Lipid T - cholesterol indices are seeming as 'atypical'.

- Lipid tri - glyceride indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Low-density lipo protein indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Very low-density lipo protein indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- High density lipo protein indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- S bilirubin total indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Creatine Phosphate K indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- CPK - muscular / brain indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- GGT indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- T - Protein indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Albumin indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- Globulin indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.
- A: G ratio indices are seeming as ‘atypical’.

Results exhibit signals for spontaneous counterfactual simulation in domain of high - level cognitive. Major finding is that entrepreneur endeavours to address choices using hematological arrangements ‘neuro - drivers’. Research discusses inferences and prospective ways to guide hematological neuroscience in choice curve. Research offers ‘First - Rate Anchorage’ of hematological arrangements ‘neuro - drivers’ and ‘entrepreneur centric choice corridor arrangements’ to appreciate how entrepreneurs make choices. Allowing for other methodologies to nature of insolent choice contours, this attempt is considered as psycho - behavioural, in that it routines wide assortment of conceptions used in behavioural scholarships, in which anthropological behaviour is reconnoitred from capacious ways.

Principal findings in this research are; entrepreneurs tend to act rationally and in their own finest interests when deciding, management researchers need to study neuromanagement in realm of entrepreneurial choice dynamics, neuromanagement provides ways of measuring entrepreneurial well-being, neuromanagement aid as a catalyst for entrepreneurial choice dynamics model development, neuromanagement offers way to test entrepreneurial centric choice models, neuromanagement improve capability to predict entrepreneurial choice dynamics behaviour, hematological provisions instrumental evidence

in entrepreneurial choice, hematological ‘tracking’ is appreciated in technopreneur choice process, hematological arrangements scrutinize choice - task approaches and cognitive capability, strong variations in hematological arrangements compartment represent choice certainty, observing hematological variables helps identify transitory situations of ambiguity and hematological arrangements serve as calculation technique beyond customary scrutiny.

Based on the analysis above it is observed that; gender of a person has statistically significant impact on Blood Glucose Random, Urea, Creatine, Sodium, Potassium, Lipid t - Cholesterol, ‘Age’ level groups have no statistical significance on any one of these characteristics, ‘stress’ has statistical significance on potassium, interaction effect of gender and stress is not statistically significant, interaction effect of age and gender is statistically significant, interaction effect of age and stress has no statistical significant, effect of ‘gender’ and interaction effect of ‘age and gender’ has influence on blood glucose random.

Results lend credence to aim of experiments undertaken in that, eye tracking methodology does help in investigating and corroborating dynamics of entrepreneurial choice making. Results exhibit substantial connection between ‘subjective’, ‘physiological’ and ‘fixations’ from real-world point of view. When entrepreneurs make choices, there’s heavy disparity in comportment. ‘Vacillating’ entrepreneurs employ additional evidence when attempting a choice compared to ‘definite’ entrepreneurs. There were differences in the manner entrepreneurs scanned available information. While ‘definite’ entrepreneurs’ spot on choice based on particular trait, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs take in all of the ‘material’. ‘Definite’ entrepreneurs perhaps opine that all options have ‘good’ and ‘bad’ characteristics. But they prefer a feature that is presumably important. ‘Vacillating’ entrepreneurs observed and opined that all ‘material’s had some quota of ‘good’ and ‘bad’ points. Secondly, ‘vacillating’ individuals distributed available time over a greater number of attributes during their course of experimental observation. The ‘definite’ participants ‘focused’ on fewer attributes in order to make their choice. Interestingly, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs spent more time overall looking at nothing. The subjects looked at ‘blank cells’ in ‘grid’ while (apparently) attempting to make a choice. This series of experiments theorises that undertaking entrepreneurs to ‘cogitate’ or ‘reframe’ selections before arriving at ‘a choice’.

Prefrontal neurons display saccade - oriented action. Appreciating how entrepreneurial brain works is significant in footings of meaningful impact on cognitive functions. Pre-saccadic activity encrypts guidelines of eye movements. Brain filters out unwanted information when entrepreneurs shift vision from one target to another focal target. Complexity of (entrepreneurial) 'intended' choice problems increases with options and features of each available option. Neuro - 'intended' choice from eye tracking processes (images and responses) to complex results, makes assumptions about how (entrepreneurs) make intended choices, defines link between (entrepreneurial) choices and (entrepreneurial) preferences. This postulates that entrepreneurs have full understanding of 'intended' choice problem and adopt optimising behaviour to create 'intended' choices. Neuro - ocular action, towards entrepreneurial- oriented behaviour, capable of explaining entrepreneurial choice making, on cognitive models of choice, recommends; escape from clichés and arrangements, challenge conventions, generate options and alternatives, strategize new designs and observe what happens and find new access opinions from which to change forward.

Eye tracking measures provide non-invasive indices of brain dynamics. Apparently, gaze examination divulges attentional and cognitive approaches. Ocular measures deliver perceptions concerning cognitive expanses. Thesis advocates auxiliary inquiries to scan physiognomies of saccade - related dynamics in prefrontal cortex and conceivable influences to eye movement mechanism and related - prefrontal functions. Eye tracking offers novel peep into choice management. It is observed that observations was correct (85%) of the time, there was effect of presence of target item and memory set size on response accuracy, real time 'inferential' data follow same pattern of effects for both factors: target presence and substantial interaction, slope was significantly influenced by target presence behavioural results, fixations could be interpreted in different ways depending on context and objective of the study, during processing of neuro - ocular scene, individuals moved eyes to relevant features in that scene, 'inferential' data from each subject was analysed independently and observed that error rates was quite low, 'entrepreneurial choice making is unswervingly inter - oriented to instantaneous accessibility, experiments reveal neurons display saccade - oriented activity, saccade - oriented activity show steering discernment and setting dependence, substantial connection between 'subjective', 'physiological' and 'fixations' from real-world point of view, 'vacillating' entrepreneurs employ additional evidence when attempting a choice, 'definite'

entrepreneurs spot on to a choice based on a particular trait, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs take in all of the ‘material’, ‘definite’ entrepreneurs, perhaps, opine that all options have ‘good’ and ‘bad’ characteristics. ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs observe and opine that all ‘material’s had some quota of ‘good’ and ‘bad’ points, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs distributed available time over a greater number of attributes during experimental observation, ‘definite’ participants ‘focused’ on fewer attributes in order to make their choice, ‘vacillating’ entrepreneurs spent more time overall looking at nothing, complexity of ‘intended’ choice problems increases with options and features of each available option, entrepreneurs have full understanding of ‘intended’ choice problem and adopt optimizing behaviour to create ‘intended’ choices.

Contributions to Knowledge

The study of entrepreneurial choice making and problem solving has attracted attention. Expanded research requires (model - based empirical) study of behavior and provide setting for basic research on how ill-structured problems are, and can be, solved. Entrepreneurial neuro - choice making, which is much less well understood than individual choice - making and problem solving, can be studied with great profit using already established methods of inquiry, especially through intensive studies.

Neuroentrepreneurial management offers solution through series of measurements of blood monikers and eye movements activity at the time of choices. It provides conceptual and philosophical framework for understanding and conducting research at intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial science, management and psychology. Neuroentrepreneurial management theory proposes to build blood monikers and eye movements-based models capable of predicting observed behaviour. Neuroentrepreneurial management sheds light on causes of behaviour (and neuroentrepreneurial anomalies) and help build theories capable of explaining and predicting choices. Measurement of blood monikers and eye movements activity provides information about underlying mechanisms blood monikers and eye movements during choice processes. Neuro - entrepreneurial choice modelling would help when new information is inconsistent with goals. Combining above disciplines stretches inter - disciplinary insight to define fundamentals of neuro - entrepreneurial choice making that has eluded researchers.

Entrepreneurial neuro - management offers insights into nature of planned rationality. Entrepreneurial neuro - management provisions data in totting to those accessible from

conjectural, experimental and investigational research on human comporment. Entrepreneurial neuro - management offers blood monikers and eye movements, eyes and blood dynamics - based solution to choice making. Outcome of study is beneficial to various stakeholders directly or indirectly associate with entrepreneurial choice actions. Study provides conceptual architectural framework for appreciation intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial science and entrepreneurial choice. Study sheds light on reasons of entrepreneurial behaviour (and incongruities) that help build theories capable of amplification and forecasting business choice. This has been the principal bed - rock of theoretical practicalities in this thesis. Dynamics of blood monikers and eye movements, blood and eye(s) activity affords information about underlying mechanisms blood monikers and eye movements, blood and eye(s) during business choice processes. Combining above disciplines gives interdisciplinary insight to define fundamentals of neuro - entrepreneurial choice making that has eluded translational researchers. This has been a primary pedestal of experimental realities in this thesis. Research findings are important as foundation for future translational research and academic plus business civilization at a large would get benefit from this study. Being a maiden study, present attempt contributes (at intersection of neuro - entrepreneurial science, management and psychology) towards existing scholarship in the following mode;

- Provide conceptual framework for conducting neuroentrepreneurial management research,
- Offer solution through neuro - based measurements at time of choice making, and
- Describe standard inter - disciplinary prototypes for choice making.
